

Andrej Poleev • Charitéplatz 1 • 10117 Berlin

Andrew M. Cuomo
Governor of New York State
Capitol Building
Albany, NY 12224
USA

3.11.2020

I write to inform you about my decision to seize assets and property of the New York Times Company, the Hearst Communications, and the Associated Press, all three are prohibited by the law of the Community Rus' in consequence of tortious acts committed by its staff and owners {1–3}, and oblige both local and federal administrations to implement said legal measures by applying appropriate laws, i.a. antitrust laws.

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Πνεῦμα κατανύξεως – a spirit of stupor, which renders their souls torpid, i. e. so insensible that they are not affected at all by the offer made them of salvation through the Messiah. The term is also related to German „geistige Umnachtung“ and „Blödsinn“ („dementia“) in psychoanalytic sense as described by Eugene Bleuler in his monograph on schizophrenia.

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Kathleen Courtney Hochul
New York State Senate
Capitol Building
Albany, NY 12248
USA

3.11.2020

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Carl E. Heastie
New York State Assembly
Capitol Building
Albany, NY 12248
USA

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Letitia James
Office of the Attorney General
The Capitol
Albany, NY 12224-0341
USA

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Keith Powers
New York City Council
Committee on Criminal Justice
New York City Hall
250 Broadway, Suite 1815
New York, NY 10007
USA

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Ritchie J. Torres
New York City Council
Committee on Oversight and Investigations
New York City Hall
250 Broadway, Suite 1759
New York, NY 10007
USA

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Dermot Francis Shea
New York City Police Commissioner
1 Police Plaza Path
New York, NY 10038
USA

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